

TOWARDS A BETTER TEACHING AND RESEARCH ACTIVITIES IN THE 21ST CENTURY: AN INVESTIGATION OF IMPACTS OF GREY LITERATURE ON THE LECTURERS OF KWARA STATE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, ILORIN.

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to investigate the influence of grey literature on teaching, learning and research activities of lecturers in College of Education, Ilorin. Data were randomly collected from selected lecturers (about 50 of them) through the questionnaire by the researcher. The data collected revealed that using frequency counts and simple percentage. The results revealed that lecturers in College of Education use grey literature materials for their research and teaching activities. The study further indicated that majority of them use the materials daily but they face the problems of identification, accessibility and organisation whenever they want to use the materials. Based on this outcome, the College library should acquire current grey literature materials -on all subject areas and should be organized well for easy accessibility and retrieval. Finally, the study recommends that the College ' library should embark on constant education of library users as the landscape of information sharing is increasing, collaborate with other libraries in resources sharing and increase its dexterity in indexing and abstracting services.

Introduction

The term grey literature brings connotations. of bleakness, apathy, indifference and questionable authority to mind, thus, it is literature that is not usually attainable through conventional channels (Augur, 1989). Debachere (1995) opined that it is

easier to describe, rather than define grey literature. However, some individuals and bodies have given different definitions of grey literature.

Grey literature are the information produced on all levels of government, academics, business and industry in electronic and print formats not controlled by commercial publicity (i.e where publishing is not the primary activity of the producing body) (Luxemburg, 1997).

In the same vein Hulte, (1991) defined grey literature materials as the quasi-printed, unpublished but circulated papers, unpublished proceedings of conferences, printed programs from conferences, and the other non-unique material which, seems to constitute the bulk of our modern manuscript collections. (p.7).

A summary of all the above definitions would place grey literature as publications issued by government, academic, business and industry in both print and electronic formats, but not controlled by commercial publishing interest and where publishing is not a primary business activity of the organisation i.e the materials which cannot readily be acquired through normal book selling channels, they are not listed in national or trade bibliographies, do not follow conventional publishing systems, and are of limited circulation. Virtually everything an individual reads outside of serials and books can be considered grey literatures.

Topology of Grey Literature

The term traditionally referred to reports, conference proceedings and doctoral theses, are the most numerous among the different types of grey literature. Others include reports, annual or activity reports, project or study reports, technical reports, reports published by ministries, laboratories or research teams. Simpson (1995).

In another development Luxemburg, (1997) identified another types of grey literature which include unpublished manuscripts, newsletters, recommendations, technical standards, patents, technical notes, product catalogues, data and statistics, presentations, malin grey literature, personal communications, working papers, house journals, laboratory research books, preprints, academic course ware, and lecture notes. (p.27).

Impact of Grey Literature on Teaching and Research Activities.

Augur (1989) considered grey literature as important primary sources of information which can fill the readers knowledge gaps by presenting the topic in greater detail and allowing the reader to gain a larger perspective on the topic. He

stated further that, it has advantage of great flexibility, speed and allow those who write and issue it to be very concise, exact and focused.

Grey literature plays a major role in informing the public and providing facts that citizens need in order to participate in government programmes and institutions that are part of their government lives (Simpson, 1995).

Schopfel (2005) opined that grey literature tends to support the disciplines they serve and do not usually present critiques or analysis of the topic.

The relative importance of grey literature largely depended on research disciplines, subjects, methodological approaches and on sources used in field of knowledge such as sciences, medical sciences, agriculture, aeronautics and engineering sciences (Sulouff, 2005).

Another great impact of grey literature can be found in folklore such areas like agriculture, arts & culture education, environmental health, and medicine, land use and land development e.t.c thus, the reports, white papers and other documents that are produced from the mentioned field of knowledge has a great deal of local knowledge which are useful to policy makers. Seeman (2002).

Objective of the Study

The objectives of the study are:

1. To investigate the purpose of grey literature in the libraries.
2. To find out how researchers use grey literature and the importance attached to teaching, learning and research purposes.
3. To examine types of grey literature its mode of organisation and identification in libraries.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raise to guide the study.

1. What are the purpose of using grey literature materials in the libraries?
2. How often do researchers use grey literature materials and for what purpose?
3. What problems do researchers encounter in using grey literature materials?

Method

The research design for this study is descriptive survey. The study focused on topology, identification and organisation of grey literature materials in the libraries.

It also investigated purpose and impact of grey literature materials on teaching, learning and research purpose.

Therefore, the researcher administered fifty questionnaires on fifty selected lecturers from the existing five schools in the College.

Result

Research question one: What are the purpose of using Grey Literature in the libraries?

Table 1: Reasons for using grey literature.

S/N	ITEMS	AGREE		DISAGREE	
		N	%	N	%
1	For teaching	30	60%	20	40%
2	For research	40	80%	10	20%
3	Relaxation	35	70%	15	30%
4	Others	32	64%	18	36%
	Specify:				
	- Preparing lecture note				
	- For advertisement				
	- Government Programme.				

The results from table one show that 60% are using grey literature for teaching purpose while 40% of the respondents disagreed that they were not using the materials for teaching. Result also shows that 80% of the respondents are using Grey Literature materials for their research purpose while only 20% disagreed with the opinion. The results shows that majority of the respondents i.e 64% of the respondents are using these grey literature materials for relaxation while 36% of the respondents disagreed that they are not using them for relaxation.

In the same table it is vividly shown that, some lecturers are using them for other purposes like checking or-knowing government programmes through gazettes, reports e.t.c. while other still use them for preparing their lecture notes and advertisement.

Research Question Two:

How often have you being using grey literature

Table 2: Level of utilization of grey literature.

S/N	ITEMS	AGREE		DISAGREE	
		N	%	N	%
1.	Daily	40	80%	10	20%
2.	Weekly	30	60%	20	40%
3.	Monthly	10	20%	40	80%
4.	Occasionally	15	30%	25	70%
5.	Annually	10	20%	40	80%
6.	Bi-Annually	14	28%	26	72%

The results as shown in table two show how often the lecturers in the College use grey literature materials. As shown on the table, 80% of the respondents agreed that they make use of the grey literature materials in the College library everyday either for preparing their lecture notes, check for government, policy, e.t.c while very few disagreed on the opinion. 60% agreed that they are using the materials on weekly basis. However, 20% of the respondents agreed that they are using grey literature on annual and monthly bases respectively, , while 30% and 28% of the respondents also agreed that they are making use of the grey literature materials occasionally and bi-annually respectively.

Research Question 3: What problems do you encountered in using grey literature materials.

Table 3: Problems encountered in using grey literature.

S/N	ITEMS	AGREE		DISAGREE	
		N	%	N	%
1.	Problem of identification	40	80%	10	20%
2.	Problems of accessibility	30	60%	20	40%
3.	Problems of organization	35	70%	15	30%

Table 3 shows problems encountered when using grey literature materials. The table shows that majority of the grey literature due to lack of identification eighty; 80% of the respondents subscribed to this view. Also, 60% agreed that they have problem of accessibility to where they are keeping or arranged these grey literature materials while 70% agreed that their own problem in using grey literature materials is 'arrangement/ organisation of the materials i.e materials cannot be easily located.

Discussion

The result of the study shows that lecturers in College of Education, Ilorin used grey literature for teaching research and learning activities. Majority of these lecturers are using them for carrying out their research activities because these grey literature materials carry recent and current information while other lecturers are using them for teaching, i.e in preparing their lecture notes, relaxation etc. This finding confirms Augur, (1989) held view that grey literature is an important primary sources of information which can fill the readers knowledge gaps by presenting the topic in greater details and allowing the reader to gain a larger perspective on the topic.

The study revealed that majority of the lecturers use grey literature materials daily for their research and teaching activities. This submission portrayed the significant impact of grey literature materials on teaching and learning process.

The study also revealed that constraints like problems of identification, lack of accessibility and organisation problems affect them in using grey literature in the libraries.

Conclusion

The study revealed that great value attached to the use of grey literature due to its significant impact on teaching, learning and research activities.

The study also revealed that grey literature carry most current information in a lucid and concise manners. However, the problem of non- accessibility, lack of identification and organisation pose a lot of challenges in using grey literature materials adequately as source materials for research.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are offered in this study:

- a. That, the college library should acquired current grey literature on different subject areas.
- b. The College library should organised the acquired grey literature materials according to classification number used in arranging book so that there -will be easy accessibility and easy retrieval of the materials.
- c. The College library should also embark on- library users' education programme so that the user will be able to identify the grey literature materials.
- d. Resource showing among the libraries through book lending, i n t e r - library co-operations, booksand publications exchange of materials on grey literature.
- e. Indexing, abstracting of grey literature materials for easy location and use.

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